

Study of new homologous series of azoester mesogens : 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-chlorobenzenes

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Homologous series 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-chlorobenzenes have been synthesized and studied with a view to understand mesomorphic characteristics of the molecule. Mesomorphic property commences from very first member of the series as enantiotropic nematic. Polymesomorphism is exhibited from dodecyl to hexadecyl derivative enantiotropically. Thermal stabilities and mesomorphic properties are discussed and compared with structurally similar homologous series.

Existence of mesomorphic state in a substance is attributed to its molecular geometry and the play of molecular forces arising therefrom. Thermotropic mesogenic substances exhibit peculiarities based on variation of temperature and range of temperature which in turn are correlated with lateral and terminal substituents in the long linear molecules like azoester mesogens. Azodyes are used in guest host interaction¹.

Results and Discussion

4-Hydroxy-3-methylphenylazo-4'-chlorobenzene is a non-mesomorphic compound. However, mesomorphism is induced by linking of a phenyl ring bridged through carboxylate central unit with *p*-substituted-*n*-alkoxy group. The transition temperatures of a homologous series are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Transition temperatures of the homologous series 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-chlorobenzenes

No of C-atoms in <i>n</i> -alkyl chain	Transition temp, °C		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1	—	151	182
2	—	130	189
3	—	121	189
4	—	114	188
5	—	112	178
6	—	106	180
7	—	81	143
8	—	78	145
10	(40) ^a	76	136
12	63	76	133
14	84	110	136
16	94	134	140

^aPredicted monotropy from phase diagram

Methyl to decyl derivatives of the series are enantiotropic nematic and rest of the homologues exhibit polymesomorphism enantiotropically. The nematic-isotropic transition curve is S-shaped (Fig. 1). The smectic nematic transition curve rises steeply as the series is ascended. Therefore, the smectic phaselength is enlarged at the cost of nematic phase as the series is ascended. The solid-mesomorphic curve shows continuous falling tendency upto dodecyl derivative with intermittent negligible rise and then rises considerably upto hexadecyl derivative. The nematic mesophase is ob-

Fig. 1. Phase transition diagram for 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-chlorobenzenes (●) solid-nematic or solid-smectic, (○) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic

served with threaded texture and smectic mesophase shows focal conic fan shaped texture of the type-A or smectic-C as judged directly from the polarizing microscope. The smectic-nematic transition curve extrapolated downward gives the value of the probable monotropic transition for decyl derivative at 40°. This value is not realizable because of high crystallizing tendency of the mesomorphic melt on cooling the nematic liquid. Nematic-isotropic transition curve shows odd-even effect with alternation of transition temperature upto octyl derivative.

Table 2 shows average thermal stabilities and the stage of commencement of smectic mesophase for the homologous series which are structurally similar, selected for comparative study.

	(1)	(A)	(B)	(C)
Nematic-isotropic or Isotropic-nematic	170.0 (C ₁ -C ₁₀)	217.6 (C ₁ -C ₁₀)	152.14 (C ₁ -C ₇)	110.2 (C ₂ -C ₆)
Smectic-nematic or Smectic-isotropic	106.6 (C ₁₂ -C ₁₆)	148.7 (C ₆ -C ₁₆)	114.66 (C ₇ -C ₁₆)	118.6 (C ₇ -C ₁₆)
Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₁₂	C ₆	C ₇	C ₇

The molecular geometry of all the homologous series

4-(4'-n-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4'-chlorobenzenes,

4-(4'-n-alkoxybenzoyloxy)phenylazo-4'-chlorobenzenes^a,

4-(4'-n-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4'-methyl-benzenes^a,

4-(4'-n-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenyl azobenzenes^a

under comparison is common, the only uncommon part being the different terminal groups [series (1), (B) and (C)] at one end. Series (1) and (A) differ with respect to lateral substitution but have same terminal end groups. Three phenyl rings linked through -COO- and -N=N- central bridges as well as left *n*-alkoxy terminal are commonly present in all the homologous series. Therefore, the overall polarity, polarizability, aromaticity etc. due to the commonly present moiety of the molecules for series (1), (B) and (C) under comparison play common role. Hence the variation that arises can obviously be traced to the different terminal groups at one end. The variation in mesomorphic characteristics between series (1) and (A) is attributed to the presence of laterally substituted CH₃ group.

Nematic-isotropic thermal transition of homologous series (1) is the highest among the group of series (1), (B) and (C) (Table 2). This can be due to the presence of H as the terminal atom at the other end of the homologous in series (C) which contributes little to the overall polarity and polarizability of the molecules in contrast to the CH₃ and Cl. Higher polarity and polarizability enhances thermal stability. Nematic-isotropic thermal stability of series (1) and (A) also differs though their terminal groups at the other end are same. The laterally substituted CH₃ group at the *ortho*-position to central carboxylate unit in case of series (1) attributes lesser lateral to terminal attractions than those attributed by the molecules of series (A). Molecules of the series (A) being long, linear and rod-like without lateral substitution can remain closer compared to the molecules of series (1). Therefore, the intermolecular attractions in case of series (A) are stronger than series (1). This reflects the relative nematic-isotropic thermal stabilities of series (1) and (A).

The order of smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic thermal stabilities for the group of homologous series (1), (B) and (C) is exactly reverse than that of nematic-isotropic thermal stabilities, i.e. smectic-nematic thermal stability of series (1) is lowest amongst the series (1), (B) and (C). Lateral attractions play greater role in determining the smectic characteristics. However, the contribution to the dipole moments of the molecules by the terminally situated group gives rise to a complicated situation because of their possible dual role in affecting both terminal and lateral attractions. The effect due to laterally situated CH₃ group in all the homologous series (1), (B) and (C) must be identical but variation in intermolecular forces of attractions may arise due to the presence of varying terminally situated groups Cl, CH₃ and H. The ratio of lateral to terminal attractions increases from series (1) to (B) to (C). This is because the change from a

ring-H to a ring-CH₃ bond (i.e. C-H to C-C bond) gradually increases the molecular polarizability and possibly also the molecular dipolarity from series (1) to (B) to (C) resulting in enhancement of thermal stabilities, particularly that of the smectic mesophase. The smectic-nematic thermal stability for series (1) is lower than for series (A) because of the branching of molecule due to laterally positioned CH₃ group in series (1) which increases the molecular separation, reducing intermolecular forces of attraction.

The study suggests that the title homologous series is of middle ordered melting type. The order for the smectic stability in presence of laterally situated CH₃ group at *ortho*-position to central bridge -COO- is H > CH₃ > Cl.

Commencement of smectic mesophase is attributed to the extent of noncoplanarity of the molecule caused by the terminally substituted group. The order of commencement of smectic phase as suggested by the study of the title series can be presented as follows in terms of terminal substitutions at the other end : H = CH₃ > Cl.

Experimental

4-Hydroxy-3-methylphenylazo-4'-chlorobenzene² and alkoxybenzoic acids³ were prepared by reported methods. Alkoxybenzoyl chlorides^{4,5,9} were directly condensed with 4-hydroxy-3-methylphenylazo-4'-chlorobenzene in dry pyridine and crystallized from alcohol. Transition temperatures were observed through a Leitz Laboulux 12 POL microscope with Kofler heating stage. Analytical data confirmed the structure.

4-(4'-n-Hexadecyloxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-chlorobenzene : Solid-smectic 94.0°, smectic-nematic 134.0° and nematic-isotropic 140.0° (Found : C, 73.12; H, 7.84; N, 4.71. C₃₆H₄₇N₂O₃Cl requires : C, 73.15; H, 7.95; N, 4.74%); δ (200 MHz, CDCl₃) 0.88 (t, CH₃CH₂ of OC₁₆H₃₃), 1.26 (s, (CH₂)_n of OC₁₆H₃₃), 1.80 (q, CH₃CH₂ of OC₁₆H₃₃), 2.33 (s, CH₃-Ar), 4.02 (t, OCH₂CH₂ of OC₁₆H₃₃), 6.95 and 6.97, 7.26 and 7.32, 7.47 and 7.50, 8.14 and 8.19 (dd, *p*-sub.), 7.81-7.89 (m, tri-sub.)

4-(4'-n-Butyloxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-chlorobenzene : Solid-nematic 114.0° and nematic-isotropic 188.0° (Found : C, 68.12; H, 5.39; N, 6.58. C₂₄H₂₃N₂O₃Cl requires : C, 68.16; H, 5.44; N, 6.62%); δ (200 MHz, CDCl₃), 1.016 (t, CH₃CH₂ of OC₄H₉), 1.541 and 1.502 ((CH₂)_n of OC₄H₉), 1.813 (t, *o*-CH₂CH₂ of OC₄H₉), 2.331 (s, CH₃-Ar), 4.064 (t, O-CH₂-CH₂ of OC₄H₉), 6.972 and 7.016, 7.257 and 7.321, 7.462 and 7.506, 7.812 and 7.845 (dd, *p*-sub.), 7.879-8.197 (m, tri-sub.).

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